

FROM SLATE TO TABLET PC: USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES TO TEACH AND LEARN LATIN AND GREEK

Abstract: New learning technologies have progressed to the point of being freely available and easy to use while adding real benefits to learning and teaching Latin and Greek. This article explores recent eLearning trends and tools as they apply to Classics.

Introduction

Pedagogy has been evolving for millennia, and instructional technology evolved along with it. One imagines a cluster of students, loins linen-swaddled, eyes aglow with wonder and fear as the Athenian sun peeks over the olive trees, illuminating the Greek scratched into wax-covered slates. The teacher collects them, reviews what each pupil wrote, praises some, and takes the switch to the rest. The slates get scraped and it's on to the next lesson.

In Asheville, North Carolina, a new Latin teacher gives his lecture on a whiteboard networked to his students' SMART AirLiner tablets. He pauses to let his student groups soak up the latest point of grammar, and then watches as they scribble with their styluses, marks appearing as if by magic on the screen at the front of the room. They have scanned dactylic hexameter correctly, and the rest of the class prepare for their turn to demonstrate what they have comprehended.

The theater in Epidaurus is packed with tourists and Greeks who have come to hear a rhapsode recite the first ten books of the *Odyssey*. His clear voice pierces the night and silences all but the cicadas, as oblivious to Homer now as they were 3,000 years ago. Listening, the ancient Greek lives like a fire, and the audience sees the wrath of Poseidon push Odysseus and his men out to sea, far, far from Ithaka.

At that same moment, students of Greek at Emory University take time in the language lab, listening to pre-recorded readings of the *Iliad*. Then they click a button on the interface in front of them and speak into the microphones attached to their headsets, mouths curving around each omicron, each omega, on pace with the passage. Recording done, each student presses "Submit" and the file is saved and logged for the instructor, who will listen to the recordings from the comfort of her home office at ten that night.

Three hours later, a student who missed her on-line Vergil class lecture downloads the podcast from the professor's web site and listens to it on her iPod, walking the dog as her professor recites the *Eclogues*. Finished with the walk, she returns to her room and logs on

to the Internet and then to Second Life for some linguistic role-playing in a virtual world, practicing her conversational Latin in real-time with voice and chat enabled as part of the Roma simulation, recording everything to digital video for a weekly project created by Vergil students in Illinois, California and Florida, all of whom are part of the same distance-learning class. Perhaps most surprising, she is unaware that she is using the most advanced and complex system for delivering education content ever devised. To her, Second Life is a given.

These students and teachers of Latin and Greek all participate in the churn of technology that assists language study. The traditional pedagogical tenets are still there: listening, reading, writing, speaking, repetition and revision, playing within a framework of grammar and vocabulary. But the pedagogical tools have changed, and will continue to change, from slate to tablet PC, from real-world practice to virtual-world role-play, from classroom lecture to recorded recitation, from solitary study to a community of learners. Technology continues to develop, and with it the techniques to learn languages. In this article, I explore some of these modern methods as they apply to classical Greek and Latin.

I. The Solitary Learner as Community Learner

When I took Latin as an undergraduate at the University of Evansville and later as a graduate student at the University of Missouri, Columbia, it was me vs. Wheelock, me vs. Petronius, me vs. Caesar. Occasionally a classmate (an art major) and I would fight in matched pairs, cramming for the weekly quiz. For midterms and finals at UE—bear in mind that this was 15 years ago—the class had an optional emergency session with the professor in the evening a couple of days before the Big Test to cram, panic and occasionally cry. Everyone came.

At Mizzou, my Ready Room was a carrel at the library, loaded with notecards. It was monastic, independent and lonely. But I did the work, and scraped an A in Latin prose. For the solitary learner, discipline is all-important, followed by an unflappable determination to never give up. Fear is also a prime motivator for the solitary learner of Latin (or at least for this author). I had a B in my first graduate-level Latin course at Mizzou. My adviser called me into his office to let me know that I really should be making better grades at this stage. He was right. Not wanting to wash out of the Masters program in art history and archaeology, I worked harder in Latin than I did for any of my seminars.

I somehow think I could have done even better, and my Latin would have been even better, had there been opportunities to share the struggle with others not just at my schools, but who were at the

same level of Latin (or beyond it), ready and eager to coach, and better yet, to practice with anyone available. While study groups still abound, there are more universal offerings to unite Latin and Greek students worldwide as they work to master their language of choice. At least six types of on-line resources exist for Classics students and their teachers, even those with little or no computer experience, or who may be initially reluctant to use computers to support their studies: discussion lists, on-line study groups, social networks, virtual worlds, and on-line games and exercises.

Discussion Lists

The e-mail discussion list is as old as e-mail itself. Why talk to one person when you can talk to dozens—even hundreds or thousands—of peers worldwide in pursuit of knowledge? Teachers need community, as their lot can be a lonely one in an underfunded and perhaps overlooked department; these lists give them a chance to exchange ideas, news, useful links for Classicists, contact information, lesson plans, teaching strategies and even whole bundles of course materials. A teacher sends an e-mail to the list's address, and that e-mail is sent to all the list's subscribers to read and perhaps reply to. For general teaching topics, there is *Latinteach*,¹ along with a handful of other lists dedicated to individual textbooks including *Oerberg*,² *Cambridge*,³ *Henle*,⁴ *Latin for Americans*⁵ and *Ecce Romani*.⁶

Recent *Latinteach* discussions have included the debate on whether or not to “dumb down” Latin (and a sidebar on today's Latin students vs. yesterday's),⁷ and an all-call for teaching materials, hand-outs, pedagogical web sites and the like for use in an on-line course for Latin-teaching methodology taught by Rick LaFleur at the University of Georgia.⁸

For *Ecce Romani*, the series' dedicated e-mail list has recently featured dialogue about exercises for Chapter 21 in conjunction with building a game of derivatives.⁹ One teacher posted her question, and several others responded quickly with answers and ideas. Other textbook-centered lists have similar conversations about points of grammar, teaching tips and requests for help.

¹ Visit <http://nxport.com/mailman/listinfo/latinteach> to subscribe to the list.

² Sign up at <http://nxport.com/mailman/listinfo/oerberg>.

³ Join other CLC users at <http://www.cambridgelatin.org/egroup.html>.

⁴ Participate in Henle-related discussions at <http://groups.yahoo.com/group/HenleLatin/>.

⁵ Sign up by visiting <http://groups.yahoo.com/group/latinforamericans/>.

⁶ Join by going to <http://groups.yahoo.com/group/ecceromani/>.

⁷ See *Latinteach* Vol. 22, Iss. 8, March 1, 2007.

⁸ See *Latinteach* Vol. 34, Iss. 2, May 21, 2007.

⁹ See *Ecce Romani* Digest 857, November 21, 2007.

For students of Greek, I have discovered no real discussion list, which may reflect the ratio of Greek to Latin courses and students. There is, however, Classical Greek's Journal,¹⁰ which invites students and teachers to ask/reply to questions relating to the study of Greek, rather than the teaching of it.

On-Line Study Groups

Those of us on diets or work-out regimens know that it is much easier to meet our nutritional and fitness goals when pushing (and being pushed by) others. So too with Classics, especially for students who are either independent or distance learners, or who are older students seeking to brush up or keep current with the Latin and Greek they had learned years ago. These study groups often act independently of formal classes.

As Greek classes are exponentially fewer in number than their Latin counterparts, these study groups are often the sole spaces for students who need a community in which to learn the language. Some examples of study groups of on-line students using the same textbook include GreekStudy (two groups go by this name),¹¹ Anamethetes (a study group linked to the eponymous text),¹² the Koine Greek Study Group,¹³ and the Homeric Greek Study Group.¹⁴

Latinists have their on-line groups, too, to study and exchange translations for peer review. Arguably the most popular is David Meadows' Atrium Latin, for students using Wheelock.¹⁵ Other Wheelock study groups are available via Latinstudy.¹⁶ In Latinstudy proper, discussion runs year-round. There is even a special, seasonal section with weekly topics surrounding summer school lessons. The list is described as "...an open mailing list dedicated to the study of Latin..."¹⁷ Latinstudy also has subgroups which, over the period when this article was written and edited, catered to students using Collins, Bradley's *Arnold*, and Bennett's *New Latin Composition*, plus more generic study groups for Vulgate and Medieval Latin, and one for Saint Augustine. Other subgroups have included Caesar's *Gallic Wars* and *Civil Wars*, Vergil's *Aeneid*, Tacitus' *Annals*, the Vulgate, Hyginus' *Fabulae*, Medieval Latin, Wheelock's *Latin Reader*, Collins'

¹⁰ <http://community.livejournal.com/classicalgreek/>

¹¹ See <http://www.geocities.com/firstgreekbook/> for information on scheduling and assignments and <http://www.quasillum.com/study/greekstudy.php> for students of Homeric, Classical and Koine Greek.

¹² See <http://groups.yahoo.com/group/anamathetes/> to become a member. There has been little activity here as this article was moving through the production process, however.

¹³ See <http://www.clients2you.com/wheelock/koine.html> for more information.

¹⁴ See <http://www.geocities.com/homericgreek/> to join.

¹⁵ <http://www atrium-media.com/latin/atriumlatin.htm>

¹⁶ <http://www.quasillum.com/latin/latin-activities.php>

¹⁷ <http://www.quasillum.com/study/latinstudy.php>

Ecclesiastical Latin, and several levels of Wheelock's Latin grammar study and *Latin Prose Composition*. Subgroups come and go, changing with the semesters and seasons, so it is wise to check the main Latin-study page to see which ones currently exist.

The best thing for students of Latin and Greek to know is that they are not alone in their pursuit of learning the language, even if neither their parents, nor their teachers, nor their friends can help.

Social Networks

Perhaps the newest—yet possibly the most predictable—on-line phenomenon is social networking. Sites like LiveJournal,¹⁸ MySpace¹⁹ and Facebook²⁰ are the most popular, creating an instant Who's Who on the Internet, a free vanity press catering to every taste, niche and clique. People seek the *polis*, and in this case they use social networks to find their way to other link-minded individuals who crave a group setting in which to discuss issues important to them as a group.

Classicists are no different. We need help. And while there are discussion lists by the dozen for Latin and for Mediterranean archaeology of all stripes, until May 2007 there were absolutely no social networks for teachers and students of Latin and Greek. That changed when I created eClassics.²¹ This social network was born out of the need to give both new and experienced Classics teachers of junior high, senior high and college Latin and Greek (and their students) a place to go to exchange ideas and inform each other about new electronic pedagogical tools to be used in the Classics classroom.²² The beauty of a Classics social network is that members can upload pictures of themselves, allowing them see who it is they are writing to, or who is posting something new. Members can add to the technology blog, discussion forums, link farm and audio/video/photo sections. The social network feeds on itself, since anyone can provide an opinion or a case study of using new technology in class (even if the technology failed), or even upload videos of class projects to inject a spirit of hope and a feeling of levity into a field sometimes perceived as a little cold.²³ In Ronnie Ancona's recent *Classical Journal* Forum article, she quotes a student as saying that the three most important characteristics of a good middle school teacher are to "be funny,"²⁴ and there is room in the social network to be just that. Exchange ideas, successes and failures informally

¹⁸ <http://www.livejournal.com>

¹⁹ <http://www.myspace.com>

²⁰ <http://www.facebook.com>

²¹ <http://eclassics.ning.com>

²² For more on eClassics, see http://www.hca.heacademy.ac.uk/resources/case_studies/A_Polis_of_Pixels_Social_Networking_for_Classics_Instructors.php.

²³ Although the piano singalong at ACL provides evidence to the contrary.

²⁴ *CJ* 102 (2006) 67–8.

with peers; learn from the process; and see what the students are doing as well. Technology can be too daunting to encounter alone, but the chances are good that someone on the social network has been there before and is willing to help.

Ultimately, a social network is just that: a network. People strike up relationships on-line and then get the chance to meet person-to-person at professional gatherings and annual meetings such as APA/AIA, ACL and CAMWS. I experienced this first-hand when an eClassics member introduced herself to me at the "Party at the Parthenon" opening reception of the 2007 ACL Institute in Nashville. As soon as I met her and learned that she had applied to her school for her first tablet PC, I was able to introduce her to two other Latin teachers I had just met who were working on technology projects for their 2007–2008 Latin classes. The three of them now maintain a steady dialogue. The virtual world is no substitute for the real world, and connections made digitally always seem to blossom after actual contact. That said, there is a steadily growing case for teaching Classics on-line through a technology that blends the real and the virtual together into a stunning, personal experience: virtual worlds.

Virtual Worlds

Social networks, on-line study groups and e-mail discussion lists all have the same limitation: conversation is not normally spontaneous or in real-time. This crucial failing changed with the introduction of virtual worlds. A virtual world is a 2-D (but usually 3-D) space accessible on-line by several people at once. Visitors can interact with one another and their environment in real-time.

The first successful application of a virtual world to Classics was VRoma,²⁵ founded on September 1, 1997, as a MOO (multi-user object-oriented database) created through a National Endowment for the Humanities Teaching through Technology Grant, and built by volunteers from colleges and high schools throughout the United States.²⁶ The virtual world, a steadily growing recreation of Rome from around 150 CE, was created as a teaching/learning environment for ancient Roman art, history, and archaeology and the Latin language.²⁷ VRoma currently boasts over 10,000 objects (ranging from buildings to pottery to papyrus) and has nearly 2,000 members. Unlike its virtual world contemporaries, VRoma will run on both modern and older computers (including those produced in the late 1990s), and requires no resource-heavy client-side software. Guest

²⁵ <http://www.vroma.org/>

²⁶ A list of participants and project directors can be found at <http://www.vroma.org/corefac.html>.

²⁷ VRoma's pedagogical objectives are detailed at <http://www.vroma.org/~bmcmanus/objectives.html>.

access is permitted, so it is possible to be a virtual tourist, learning about artifacts, chatting with other VRoma users and receiving in-world updates through a windowpane.

The Classical scholarship in VRoma is vast and interconnected, allowing visitors to learn about the context in which they are immersed. The data are correct, and while the world is not 3-D and cannot be navigated by the current trends of “real-time movement” or via a keyboard’s arrow keys, a wealth of photos can be viewed and explored. One moves from one area to the next by clicking on objects, or by typing in a dedicated panel (example: “east”). As with any learning exercise, content is key, and VRoma provides ample content to its users, allowing them to help make contact with the art, archaeology, history and language of Rome even more immediate.

Contemporary hardware and software have enabled other modern virtual worlds to become what people have dreamed of: real-time, 3-D environments that look real, can be navigated by walking/driving/flying, and allow conversation via computer microphone. The most popular and successful of these, *Second Life*²⁸ and its counterpart for children aged 13–17, *Teen Second Life*,²⁹ have existed in cyberspace since 2003. From the crucible of William Gibson’s *Neuromancer* and Neil Stephenson’s *Snow Crash* comes a 3-D on-line world of avatars (3-D idealizations or fantasies of residents) and their creations (anything from a pair of wings, to a house, to a fantastical reconstruction of ancient Rome). Residents in *Second Life* interact with one another on-line in real-time using chat, instant messaging and, as of July 10, 2007, voice-chat, as they navigate the Grid³⁰ in search of wondrous things to explore.

The applications for education are obvious, and an entire subculture of educators have flocked to the *Second Life* Educators digest (SLED)³¹ and *Sloodle* (a combination of *Second Life* and the Moodle course management system).³² Within that subculture is a smaller niche of language educators who have turned *Second Life* into a playground for interacting with people from other cultures and countries.³³ Teachers are taking their classes on in-world safaris to places frequented by native German-, Spanish- or French-speakers. At some times of day, the virtual Roma sim (short for

²⁸ <http://www.secondlife.com>

²⁹ <http://teen.secondlife.com>

³⁰ The “Grid” is the shorthand way of saying “*Second Life*’s virtual environment”—the map of the land in *Second Life* actually looks like a grid.

³¹ Subscribe for free and participate in the forums by visiting <http://www.simteach.com/forum/>.

³² Visit <http://www.sloodle.org> and <http://www.moodle.com> for more information.

³³ *Second Life Languages* is a Yahoo!-based discussion list dedicated to creating and exploring tools for teaching language within the scope of this virtual world. Access the group by visiting <http://groups.yahoo.com/group/secondlifelanguages/>.

“simulation”) is populated by real-world Italians touring an ancient version of their capital city.³⁴ Visit the Steki Epicurean beach sim to speak modern Greek with modern Greeks,³⁵ the hospitality is instant, exactly as one might expect.³⁶

Second Life does blend reality with fantasy, and visitors to Roma will notice that the virtual version is not—nor does it claim to be—an entirely faithful recreation of the ancient city. Instead, the site blends Roman elements of art and architecture from various periods and places into something universally “Roman” in pursuit of promoting Roman culture and history. Teachers will need to voice the same caution to their students that they use when discussing Wikipedia: critical thinking is required. Second Life members, however, do have the opportunity to correct mistakes and construct their own, true-to-Rome artifacts, clothing and more. The free togas distributed to first-time visitors to Roma can be modified. Over time, I hope that the inaccuracies of virtual Rome will be corrected, but they should not detract from using this as a place to practice conversational Latin and even Greek with classmates.

For Classicists, the study of Greek and Latin can be facilitated in Second Life in a way that no traditional classroom could attempt. Students can create their own avatars; dress them in togas, armor or *peploi*; and role-play in the language they are learning, by either typing or speaking, conversing in real-time. Class projects can include machinima (computer-generated films recorded live and on-line), allowing students in Second Life to reenact the assassination of Julius Caesar, a day in the Curia, or even the Battle of Aigospotami. The teacher provides the framework and then lets the students loose within that framework to fill the space with the language they are learning, practicing on one another under the guidance of the teacher or even as, God-forbid, homework that proves engrossing and addictive.

The environments and technologies for using Second Life for languages classes have already been realized and are in active use, albeit primarily by modern languages. Learning how to use Second

³⁴ Tour the Roma sim in Second Life by teleporting to this SLURL (Second Life URL): <http://slurl.com/secondlife/Roma/232/40/22/?title=ROMA>. Note that Roma in Second Life contains some mature themes, including a temporary exhibit on ancient erotic art housed in the virtual Capitoline Museum (as of November, 2007). By contrast, VRoma is suitable for all ages.

³⁵ Teleport using this SLURL: http://slurl.com/secondlife/Hellas_/48/200/21/?title=Steki on Epicurus Beach.

³⁶ To access either Second Life or Teen Second Life, download the “Second Life Client,” a software program roughly 34 MB for Windows or 71 MB for Macintosh. One must also create an on-line identity (avatar). Both the software and avatar are free, as is touring the Grid. Creating/purchasing/renting buildings, art, vehicles, clothing and the like, costs money (Linden Dollars, which are about one third of a US dollar). Second Life runs well on computers purchased since 2005, but has issues on Windows Vista.

Life will naturally take some time, regardless of the language being studied, but the learning curve is not that steep. Teachers of Latin and Greek can organize class field trips on a monthly basis to practice in-world conversational language skills, and can encourage in-world homework assignments, or recommend that class projects be produced within Second Life. With programmers and at least one publishing company building a Classical presence within Second Life, the burden of creating a space for learning language has been removed from individual instructors and provided at no cost to visitors.³⁷ As more teachers and students of Latin and Greek discover Second Life and begin to use it for language study, the virtual Classical world can be updated to more accurately reflect ancient Greek and Roman material culture. As with the Wikipedia, we can accept what is on-line, dismiss it out-of-hand, or be proactively improve the existing content. Ideally, the quality Classical content of VRoma could be merged with the multimedia interface of Second Life, creating a true virtual Rome, accurately and fully realized, ready for its Latin-speaking inhabitants and for interested visitors, tourists, philologists and archaeologists.

Second Life lends itself to a positive kind of addiction, allowing users to explore new worlds and seek out new civilizations. But this is real, not science fiction. Massive Multi-Player On-Line Role-Playing Games like World of Warcraft³⁸ have sucked up the brain-power and discretionary time of millions of people, old and young, worldwide. Introduce a similar interface to young Classics students and watch as they create authentic reconstructions of ancient buildings, clothing, art, secular architecture and more, exploring one another's sims and participating in on-line meet-ups and other events.

Robert Welch University³⁹ is the first school in the world to offer an on-line major in Classics featuring courses that include regular journeys into Second Life to an eLearning island called EduNation.⁴⁰ The school has rented space for teaching Latin here, giving students from around the world a place to play and interact within the constructs of the language. Other schools such as the University of Central Missouri have been using Second Life for language

³⁷ Bolchazy-Carducci Publishers has created an on-line learning space in Second Life in support of its new course of Latin study, *Latin for the New Millennium*, where students and teachers using the textbooks can visit and learn/practice Latin by playing in this environment. To visit the site, navigate to this SLURL (Second Life URL): <http://slurl.com/secondlife/ROMA%20Subura/50/146/24>.

³⁸ Visit the World of Warcraft on-line community site at <http://www.worldofwarcraft.com/index.xml>. There is a Latin-speaking guild (Horde faction), *Carpe Praedam*, managed by Philabovis (this author). Mail him in-game for an invite to join the guild.

³⁹ <http://www.robertwelchuniversity.org/courses.php?ccid=14>

⁴⁰ The EduNation SLURL is <http://slurl.com/secondlife/Education/67/47/22/>.

education for over a year,⁴¹ but Robert Welch University is the first to offer anything Classics-related. It is my hope that other universities and secondary schools follow this lead.

All of the above Internet resources cater to community-based learning. Language, after all, is the key to communicating with others. If we as educators wish to make Greek and Latin come alive for our students, the best way is to engage them—and have them engage themselves—in real-time dialogue, creating conversations organically with the vocabulary and grammar they have learned so far, enjoying the moment, making mistakes and learning from them, much like a tourist new to a foreign country. The initial, clunky approach to a language gets refined as more time is spent in the country.

On-Line Games and Exercises

The above resources can all be lumped under the heading of “communal” learning tools; they are intended to be shared by creators and guests, working together toward a greater understanding of Classics. Some newer resources (e.g. social networks and virtual worlds) can be classed as Web 2.0 tools, on-line elements that are almost Freirean, making teachers students, and students teachers. But what of teachers and students who have no time to explore, are skeptical of new and emerging technologies and how they can be applied to a classroom environment, or who have a natural abhorrence of anything technical but realize there might be some good in it, if they just knew where to look?

That teachers have no time is a universal. My brother is a high school math teacher, and my wife is a university professor, and neither of them have what could be called “discretionary time.” Many on-line learning tools are therefore overlooked not because they are perceived as hard to use, or are deemed, sight unseen, to be novelties, but because there is no time in the day to get to them after with papers to read, tests to grade, office hours to keep, lessons to plan, meetings to attend, and perhaps a few minutes with the family. In order to provide teachers with immediate access to Latin and Greek resources, many publishers and independent teachers began posting lesson plans, syllabi, exercises, drills and games on the Internet, often free of charge. Several of these sites are easy to find and use, and most have a home-grown associated with websites created by non-technical people working at midnight in an attempt to offer solid content to their peers, and driven by a combination of love and necessity. These sites are not only time-savers for teachers, but offer quality content to students as well, to use either at home or even during class (especially in classrooms that simultaneously host

⁴¹ See <http://engl1030sl.blogspot.com/> for more information.

more than two levels of Latin at the same time). A quick Google search for “Latin exercises” or “Greek resources” will return hundreds of hits. I list some of the more stable and popular sites below, Greek first.

Greek On-Line Exercises, Drills and Resources

The metasite Greek Grammar⁴² is probably the most complete free, on-line educational resource for Greek, loaded with links not only to elementary (introductory-level) sites, but also to sites with annotated texts.

Greek-Language.com is a one-stop resource for grammars and other learning materials for various levels of students of Classical and Koine Greek.

The University of Edinburgh Department of Classics homepage⁴³ has links to its individual Greek classes, the first two semesters of which have hand-outs (including tutorials, exercises and handbooks). There are also links to fonts.

Textkit⁴⁴ is a web site dedicated to both Latin and Greek on-line learning. Several downloadable tutorials for Greek are available here, including the Greek Aspect and Aorist Morphology.

The University of Chicago has dozens of “nifty Greek handouts” on various parts of speech.⁴⁵

The University of Kentucky⁴⁶ provides handouts that introduce elementary Greek pronunciation and letter forms, plus MP3 files to assist students with Greek pronunciation.

UC Berkeley has a quite complete set of downloadable teaching materials for ancient Greek.⁴⁷

BiblicalGreek.org⁴⁸ is a good metasite for links to Greek pedagogical resources.

C.W. Conrad at Washington University has posted PDFs of his teaching materials for both ancient and Koine Greek on-line.⁴⁹

Latin On-Line Exercises, Drills and Resources

Several Latin textbooks have dedicated webpages for exercises relating to their content. Some publishers provide these sites for their readers, while other textbook-related drill-sites were created and are managed independently by individual teachers.

⁴² <http://perswww.kuleuven.be/~u0013314/greekg.htm>

⁴³ <http://www.shc.ed.ac.uk/classics/undergraduate/greek/greek.htm>

⁴⁴ <http://www.textkit.com/tutorials/>

⁴⁵ <http://humanities.uchicago.edu/depts/classics/People/Faculty/helmadik/>

⁴⁶ <http://www.uky.edu/AS/Classics/greek/>

⁴⁷ http://socrates.berkeley.edu/~Eancgreek/ancient_greek_start.html

⁴⁸ <http://www.biblicalgreek.org/grammar/>

⁴⁹ <http://www.ioa.com/%7Ecwconrad/current.html>

Cambridge University is responsible for the Cambridge Latin Course materials and has provided hundreds of questions, exercises, drills and games on-line.⁵⁰

Robert Cape of Austin College has produced a comprehensive set of resources and exercises in support of the Oxford Latin Course.⁵¹ Created with the aid of private grants, his workbook is the most valuable on-line destination for teachers and students using the Oxford course.

The official website for Wheelock's Latin⁵² contains links to several on-line study helps, as well as resources available for purchase.

Ecce Romani has a number of websites dedicated to helping students with Latin grammar. The official site hosted by Pearson Prentice Hall has dedicated exercises for each chapter in the series.⁵³ Gil Lawall manages an independent *Ecce* site⁵⁴ solely for teachers, which serves as a clearinghouse of lesson plans, teaching tips, and other teaching materials.

Users of Oerberg's *Lingua Latina* (and also Wheelock) can find conjugation exercises on Mike Wilson's Latin page.⁵⁵ This appears to be the only Oerberg on-line resource at this time.

Latin for Americans also has a website of exercises and drills created by Magistra Rebecca Bush of Hamilton Southeastern High School.⁵⁶ While intended for her introductory Latin classes, these exercises are freely available and can be used by others working with *LFA*.

Looking at Latin is a comprehensive Latin grammar published by Bolchazy-Carducci Publishers and can be used with any Latin textbook series. Bolchazy-Carducci is producing over 6,000 on-line exercises illustrating all aspects of Latin grammar which will be launched at ACL 2008. A few examples are currently available for review.⁵⁷

For drills, exercises and helps for teachers not tied to any particular program of study, Rose Williams, who has been teaching Latin "for a very long time" (her words) to anyone who will listen, has numerous PDF handouts available for download.⁵⁸

Jim McKeown teaches Latin at the University of Wisconsin, Madison, and has created his own Latin exercises for his students that are paired with wondrous—and at times horrific—unique passages from ancient Latin authors.⁵⁹

⁵⁰ http://www.cambridgescp.com/page.php?p=clc^oa_intro^intro

⁵¹ <http://artemis.austincollege.edu/acad/cml/rcape/latin/>

⁵² <http://www.wheelockslatin.com/wheelocklinks.htm>

⁵³ <http://www.phschool.com/webcodes10/index.cfm?fuseaction=home.gotoWebCode&wcprefix=jgk&wcsuffix=1000>

⁵⁴ <http://www-unix.oit.umass.edu/~glawall/ecceteach.html>

⁵⁵ <http://funarg.nfshost.com/r2/code/languages/conjugations.html>

⁵⁶ http://www.hse.k12.in.us/staff/RBUSH/latin_i_practice.htm

⁵⁷ <http://www.bolchazy.com/prod.php?cat=latin&id=6153>

⁵⁸ <http://www.roserwilliams.com/teachingaids.html>

⁵⁹ <http://www.jcmckeown.com/>

One of the most comprehensive metasites dedicated to Latin is run by Bruce R. Magee.⁶⁰ Wheelock-related teaching materials, plus syllabi, links to grammars, exercises and games await visitors.

Latinteach, while known mostly as an e-mail discussion list, also has a webpage dedicated to on-line Latin resources for teachers.⁶¹

Homegrown Romans is a Latin drill-site for students preparing for the National Latin Exam and Certamen. There are also exercises here for mythology, Greek history and Roman daily life.⁶²

The Classical Studies department at Cornell College in Iowa has created a number of on-line resources for learning and retaining Latin.⁶³ The page of mnemonics is good for remembering the subjunctive, third declension genders, the Roman calendar and more. There is also a second page with tips for “learning Latin with less stress,” allowing students to “go to class happy, relaxed and prepared.”⁶⁴

One of the best and most comprehensive sites for on-line Latin drilling and games is Quia.⁶⁵ Dozens of Latin teachers have created thousands of quizzes, exercises and games, which are freely available for other teachers and students to use.

Grammar and vocabulary exercises are not the only on-line resources for students and teachers of Latin. The gold standard for a web translation resource for intermediate as well as more advanced students is the *Online Companion to the Worlds of Roman Women*.⁶⁶ Ann R. Raia and Judith Lynn Sebesta created the site in support of the book, and it has grown through collaboration with other high school- and college-level Latin teachers to contain a compilation of Latin texts relating to women. The texts include commentary, hyper-linked vocabulary and translation aids, and images. There is also a section for instructional materials.

When casual or reluctant Internet users see the value inherent in any of these static on-line resources, perhaps they will consider dipping their toes into the waters of Web 2.0, lurking on (or even joining) eClassics, or creating an avatar to explore VRoma and Second Life. The best-case scenario is to have someone collect and connect Latin and Greek instructors worldwide into a single space where they can communicate with one another in their common language, exchange teaching materials, war stories, ideas and more to help one another get through another semester while discovering how to use new technologies to enhance language-learning, blending

⁶⁰ http://garts.latech.edu/bmagee/latin/latin_links.htm

⁶¹ http://www.latinteach.com/Site/RESOURCES/Entries/2007/10/5_Latin_Quizzes_and_Games.html

⁶² <http://www.homegrownromans.info/>

⁶³ http://www.cornellcollege.edu/classical_studies/latin/mnemonic.shtml

⁶⁴ http://www.cornellcollege.edu/classical_studies/latin/tips.shtml

⁶⁵ <http://www.quia.com/shared/latin/>

⁶⁶ <http://www.cnr.edu/home/sas/araia/companion.html>

what is new and practical with traditional book-and-classroom instruction. There will be teachers who self-select as content-producers who can drive this engine for teachers who have neither the time nor inclination to contribute, yet require help to prepare for class. This is no different from the differentiation between readers and writers. But with the Internet trending towards collaboration by all, we may see more and more reader-writers and writer-readers. People have things to say and things to share, and the Internet is becoming increasingly easy to use and maintain. A desire to share knowledge mixed with the ease-of-use of Web 2.0 tools cannot help but enable Classicists to join their peers on-line.

While these on-line exercises, drills and teacher resources are useful, many were created and are maintained (and occasionally updated) by individuals as opposed to schools or companies. There is the danger that these valuable, independently created teaching materials will disappear when their creators retire, die, lose interest in keeping the content current, or stop paying the hosting fees for their sites. By sharing exercises and drills within the context of a social network or some kind of Classics portal (perhaps like the one being constructed by the American Philological Society), we can guard against this loss of knowledge, preserving and updating these activities for future generations of teachers and students.

III. Meeting student expectations for classroom technology vs. meeting teacher expectations for language learning

Students want what they want. They appreciate both the familiar and the new. When my elementary school got its first computer, all of the children crowded around it while one uppity seven-year-old bragged that he could make it talk. "Go ahead," we said. He began typing, green letters on a black screen:

```
10 ? "Hello"  
20 goto 10
```

He executed the statement and the computer said hello to all of us kids, standing there in a semi-circle. I don't recall there being any teachers present.

A few years later, one uppity nine-year-old came to recess wearing headphones so small they hardly covered his ears. Everyone wanted to know what was going on. Where was the radio? The boy had the first Sony Walkman (a WALKMAN, not a portable tape player/radio), and he begrudgingly let us listen to about 30 seconds of some Journey song before giving us the boot.

When I was in drama class, I read my parts into the crummy microphone attached to a tape recorder the size of a shoebox, and

would played the tape back in my WALKMAN (no knock-off for me, thanks), back and forth on the bus, on my bike, on a run. I used the thing to learn, to get the words and phrases into my brain.

As with most new technologies, play came first, and then a more sober, practical application. I learned to code BASIC and Pascal, which prepared me for learning German and Latin grammar. I remember asking a fellow high school freshman, prior to my initiation into *How Computers Work*, what good computers were going to be. He blithely replied, "Games! And spreadsheets, I guess." Great. What's a spreadsheet?

I imagine that today's students are no different than we were 30 years ago. I can apply my toys to serious pursuits, and use them to learn. With computers we have the Internet. We have instant information via Google and the Wikipedia,⁶⁷ but we also have immediate access to places like the Latin Library,⁶⁸ to Perseus,⁶⁹ to tools we never dreamed of when we were flogging Wheelock.⁷⁰ And, instead of the Walkman, we have the ubiquitous iPod (no generic MP3 players for us, please—make ours Apples), and we still listen to the radio, albeit in pre-recorded podcasts, and are still fed Latin through our ears courtesy of rhapsodes like Robert Sonkowsky.

With games and social networking sites, the expectation is developing that game theory is the new, new thing in education. MIT's New Media Consortium⁷¹ has an entire arm dedicated to studying gameplay as a learning tool. LanguageLab.com, a commercial venture, is developing language learning tools via Second Life that get kids out of the read/write/regurgitate classroom rut, and into virtual space where they can begin to treat the language as organic and three-dimensional. Any teacher can take this teaching theory of "practicing language in space" into Second Life and create moderated scenarios in which students can speak, avoiding the classroom setting in favor of a more Classical dialogue under an

⁶⁷ Not to mention the all-Latin Vicipaedia, http://la.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pagina_prima, and the ancient Greek Ouikipaideia, <http://incubator.wikimedia.org/wiki/Wp/grc>.

⁶⁸ The Latin Library is a repository of Latin texts that can be read on-line for free at <http://www.thelatinlibrary.com/>.

⁶⁹ The Perseus Project contains a large, ever-growing database of images and text related to the Classical world, <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/>. The comprehensive nature of Perseus, however, can be overwhelming. Besides Perseus and the Latin Library, other sites containing primary texts in Classical and Medieval Latin include: <http://www8.georgetown.edu/departments/medieval/labyrinth/display.cfm?Action=View&Category=Latin>. Georgetown also has a bonanza of links to Latin manuscripts, for those interested in paleography as a pedagogical tool: <http://www8.georgetown.edu/departments/medieval/labyrinth/display.cfm?Action=View&Category=Manuscripts>.

⁷⁰ See the Wheelock on-line resources page at <http://www.wheelockslatin.com/wheelocklinks.htm>.

⁷¹ <http://www.nmc.org/>

olive tree. The desire to learn is still very much with the students, and they expect to use the technology they have already adopted to help them learn. Arguably one of the biggest challenges to teachers is to keep up and let the technology be a bridge instead of a wall to language-learning.

But is this really true? One of the questions (it has many variations) I ask of all new members who join the eClassics social network is, "Do you use (or expect to use) technology to help you learn Latin and/or Greek?" Many members don't reply. Some students reply with an "oh, please" and admit to going on-line themselves for help, while noting that tech is not present in class (and not encouraged outside of class). Some members state that they would like to use technology, but fear they would spend too much time fumbling with it, for it to be much help. Some students say they like learning with the SMART Board. But, by and large, the students—at least the ones studying Classics—are still very much into the tradition and ritual of school. They are still book-trained almost exclusively. Most of the language labs still have cassettes and big, clumsy plastic headsets that are painful to wear. It may be that if the school or school system adopts new technology for itself, things trickle down to the teacher and ultimately to the students, who finally realize that they can listen to both Catullus *and* Linkin Park on their iPods.⁷²

This places teachers in a dilemma. Some school systems adopt technology and cram it down the throats of the faculty. This causes resentment and resistance, and leads to poor morale, IT mistakes, impatience, and frustration that can be easily read by the students, especially upon hearing certain non-Latin, one-syllable utterances.⁷³ Other teachers want to employ tech, but cannot convince the school (or district) to go for it. Some schools adopt tech and then drop it after a one- to two-year testing period.⁷⁴

In all of these scenarios, the need for pedagogy is lost in the technology shuffle. People forget what the technology is for and who will be using it. The primary question in implementing into an educational environment should be "How can this help my students learn?", followed immediately by "Can this technology help my students learn better than my old method?", and finally by "Does this technology make my life as a teacher easier/better?"

⁷² Haverford College has a clearinghouse of Latin podcast links at <http://www.haverford.edu/classics/audio/>. Classics scholars can also benefit from the vast collections of Latin podcasts administered by Evan Millner at <http://latinum.mypodcast.com>. Chris Francese at Dickinson College produces high-quality Latin poetry podcasts with regularity at <http://blog.dickinson.edu/?cat=815>.

⁷³ This was confessed to me by an eClassics member during an on-line conversation.

⁷⁴ See the article, "Laptops in classroom not working out as hoped," *Wall Street Journal* (October 14, 2005).

With all the new tools that are out there, we are witnessing a sort of technological Darwinism, in which clunky, inefficient technologies are washing out of the gene pool in favor of user-friendly interfaces and one- or two-button gadgets. Pushing the technology to become more transparent and easier to use can only help teachers, who often find themselves struggling to figure out the first steps of going on-line, or of preparing a lecture to broadcast via data projector. The iPod has come close to setting a gold standard for hand-held devices. Simple Web browsers like Firefox are enabling more non-technical people to surf for information. I have often heard that in this Information Age, we are a “culture of amateurs,” in that everyone can contribute to any information stream, which is then vetted by the hive-mind of user-groups and social networks, creating solid, accurate content in a short period of time. Information has become the province of the mob, but is almost Utopian in its democratic insistence on approving/ vetoing the data that appear.

I challenge Classics teachers to find their way to new technology and play with it. 100% book-learning is dead. Even the centuries-old Classics publishing mother-ships Oxford and Cambridge have sets of on-line helps and drills. *Latin for Americans* and *Ecce Romani* have active user groups and discussion lists. *Looking at Latin* has on-line exercises under development. An on-line “Teachers’ Lounge” is being built for *Latin for the New Millennium*. We cannot and should not prohibit the new language pedagogy from seeping into our classrooms, and must make the switch from seeing ancient languages as two-dimensional, to be studied via books and lecture only. The new electronic, on-line tools add a third dimension, a new way to learn.

IV. *Looking to the future: digital divide vs. digital parity*

One of the main concerns articulated to me in discussions with teachers is what I call “digital parity.” If we require students to use technology from home in order to participate in class, we must ensure that everyone has a computer and Internet access, and can access it for some minimum number of minutes a day for classwork. And the question of the availability of technology has been answered, we must either cater to the lowest denominator or provide resources to upgrade students still working on Windows 95 computers with dial-up Internet access to at least Windows XP Home with DSL. Where will the money come from to either upgrade or sponsor the hardware for students?

Even if the technology, moreover, is identical from student to student (and from student to teacher), not everyone in a class will have the same level of techumen. Some students will end up spending as much time learning about IT as they will learning Latin.

Some would call that a bad thing, but I am not sure this is true. We live in a digital age where technology is omnipresent. If students need to play catch-up, let them (and help them) so that they are better prepared for college and future employment. The same holds true for teachers who are self-proclaimed “computer illiterates.” If my 72-year-old father-in-law can learn Windows XP, Microsoft Office and Internet Explorer 7, anyone can. You do your students a favor by keeping up with technology.

The so-called digital divide is real. I have to keep explaining to people ages 60 and up what an avatar is, what a podcast is, what an iPod is, what a course management system is.⁷⁵ They want to learn, and I am happy to teach.

In Classics, as in other fields, there are four classes of technology user: experts (the creators of tools we use to further our study), casual users (those who take advantage of the new tools to conduct classes and research more easily), newbies (or “n00bs,” people who have made a leap of faith and are willing to try and either succeed or fail at using technology) and Luddites (those with a strong bias against or fear of technology).⁷⁶ All four classes of users help advance the state of technology in any field. The experts are driven by the need to create new tools to help themselves and others. The casual users vet these new initiatives and separate the good from the bad. The newbies further test technology, selecting that which is easy both to learn and use. And the Luddites are arguably the most important caste of all, since it is from them that newbies are converted. As producers and consumers of technology, we must try to appease the Luddite faction to demonstrate the value of any new advance in technology. By paying attention to each audience, the field grows as it creates and adopts new tools for teaching and learning.

The Perseus Project is an excellent example of the this system working to produce better digital resources for Classicists. In their words, “Perseus is an evolving digital library, engineering interactions through time, space, and language. Our primary goal is to bring a wide range of source materials to as large an audience as possible. We anticipate that greater accessibility to the sources for the study of the humanities will strengthen the quality of questions, lead to new avenues of research, and connect more people through the connection of ideas.”

⁷⁵ An avatar is a 3-D on-line presence in a virtual environment; a podcast is a pre-recorded radio-style program available for download to a computer or portable media player; an iPod is a handheld media player produced by Apple that has cornered the market on devices that play digital audio and video; a course management system (CMS) is an on-line tool for teachers to administer their classes via the Internet, and for students to use to access course content and upload homework assignments and tests.

⁷⁶ For a brief history of Luddism, see <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Luddite>.

On-Line Collaboration as the Bridge over the Digital Divide

The Perseus Project, although hosted by Tufts University, is a true group effort with a noble goal. From the site: "Perseus has collaborated with many institutions and individuals since serious development began in 1987. Our goals have, however, remained consistent. We are dedicated to making the best possible materials available to the widest possible audience. While we seek to enhance student learning and faculty research, we have found that electronic publication allows us to go beyond the reach of conventional academic publication." This type of collaborative project goes one step further into the realm of content generated by interested parties via more personal vehicles of content generation: wikis and blogs.

Wikis

"Wikipedia," a household word since at least 2005, is an open source encyclopedia available in dozens of languages that allows anyone to create, add or edit content on any subject. The main page for Classics is at <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Classics>, and features a definition of Classics, with links to many other pages of useful information about philosophy, language and culture in the ancient Mediterranean world. The main argument against Wikipedia is also the core of its strength: anyone can add to it. So who's minding the store? Like articles submitted to scholarly publications (such as this one), articles are constantly peer-reviewed by editors-at-large and other enthusiasts. The information sorts itself out over time. Students should nonetheless be cautioned about the accuracy of some of the data, and should perhaps use Wikipedia only as a starting point for learning about ... almost anything. Teachers should also issue a warning about Wikipedia and plagiarism: do not copy Wikipedia articles as your own for class papers. Open source does not mean "free to publish as one's own," but it does mean the content can be shared and built upon.

What many people do not realize is that wikis go beyond Wikipedia. Since Wikipedia cornered the market—which is ironic, given that it is, by its nature, free—as an almost Borgesian invention of knowledge creation, storage and retrieval, the concept of wikis has exploded as well. Most wikis allow anyone to quickly add content about anything, and this information is then edited and expanded by others. Wikis are thriving within Classics, and many offer free membership, once you are confirmed by the wiki's gatekeeper. What follows are some examples of Classics wikis with a pedagogic angle.

The Latin Wikipedia, called *Vicipaedia*,⁷⁷ contains nearly 14,000 entries written entirely in Latin. A search for Gaius Valerius Catullus retrieved his biography, an image of the poet, links to various poems and to sites containing Catullus' collected works, and more.

eClassics regular contributor Laura Gibbs is a fan of the wiki and has at least one of her own that she manages through a free service called pbwiki.⁷⁸ As a distance learning educator, she has taken a fun and useful pedagogical approach to learning Latin via proverbs and fables. The proverbs approach has its own wiki.⁷⁹

Also in Latin pedagogy, an anonymous Latin teacher has posted an open source Latin textbook project as a "wikibook," an open source eBook⁸⁰ that can be viewed and edited by anyone wishing to help.

There is a future to Classics wikis, too. I had the occasion to speak with Chris Francese of Dickinson College at the 2007 ACL Institute, and he reminded me of the potential of the wiki regarding Classical authors. Many authors already have their own pages in the Wikipedia. It is up to Classicists to flesh out these pages, add others, provide links, translations, history, historiography, paleography, images and the like, to build up a collaborative and organic resource for teachers to use in their classes.⁸¹

Blogs

The other free technology actively used by Classicists in the classroom is the blog. "Blog" is a shortened form of "web log," in effect a kind of on-line diary generally open to the public via blogging sites like LiveJournal,⁸² Wordpress⁸³ and Blogger.⁸⁴ In the past few years, educators have begun introducing blogs into their day-to-day classroom routine. Three recent examples merit mention here, as they are all significant and innovative contributions to digital pedagogy and Classics, and are all quite different from one another.

Those of you who subscribe to the Latinteach discussion list⁸⁵ have been treated to real eLearning in action in a high school Latin classroom, specifically Latin 3 (AP Catullus). The teacher is Robert

⁷⁷ http://la.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pagina_prima

⁷⁸ <http://pbwiki.com>

⁷⁹ <http://latinviaproverbs.pbwiki.com/>

⁸⁰ <http://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/Talk:Latin>

⁸¹ Francese's own "trial attempts at wikidom," as he describes them, can be found at <http://vergilsaeneid.wetpaint.com/>, where he has done a few notes for Book 10, based on public domain sources, and a Catullus site developed by a couple of his "very industrious" students at http://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/The_Poetry_of_Gaius_Valerius_Catullus. Ronnie Ancona of Hunter College (CUNY) also has a wiki dedicated to teaching Catullus at <http://writingpassion.pbwiki.com>.

⁸² <http://livejournal.com>

⁸³ <http://wordpress.com>

⁸⁴ <http://blogger.com>

⁸⁵ See n. 1, above.

Patrick (aka Magister Patricius), and his blog, *Carmina Catulli*,⁸⁶ is used by his students to reflect on the poems presented in class. Attention is paid not just to the grammar, but to the construction of each poem and how the writing supports the overall theme and meaning. This kind of synthesis produces lifelong Latin readers, rather than Latin students who cram and regurgitate. Granted, a solid Latin foundation is required to get to the point where one can read and interpret (and thus answer Magister Patricius' questions), but this school appears to have it right. The blog supplements classroom instruction, encourages dialogue and active participation, and draws both students and teacher together into understanding some of the greatest poetry ever put to papyrus. The technology is simple and effective, requires little in the way of technical knowledge, and has a clearly defined focus. I highly recommend that you take a look at it and then consider setting up one (it's free) for your own classes at any level. For the fall 2007 semester, Magister Patricius will be blogging for his AP Vergil class.

Another pre-college Latin teacher, Emily Silverman, taught Latin at the William Penn Charter School in Philadelphia during the 2006–07 school year. One of her classes created a rather dynamic site on Wordpress⁸⁷ focusing on Vergil's *Aeneid*. Over the course of a semester, each of Silverman's students adopted the *persona* of a character in the epic and wrote a blog in the character's voice. Her current students are in love with the project, and past students wish they had had a project like this when they were enrolled (how often does that happen?). From her "About..." page:

Once upon a time, not long ago, a couple of students were joking about making Facebook pages for Dido and Aeneas or setting them up on Match.com. Ha ha ... ah ha! This project starts here and moves forward and upwards and backwards. Creativity, recollection of the *Aeneid* and research into other arts and letters are all here. Had we more time, I'd tighten the ties to the Latin in selections from the *Aeneid*, probably asking them to provide their own translations and podcasting their reading in Latin and English. You'll note when you look at the blogs (see the blogroll for links) that there is tremendous flexibility. As long as I could see the connection, or the connection was made clear, it worked for me. The students, by and large, are about as engaged and connected as I could possibly wish. Not only have many added above and beyond the basic requirements, they talk about their characters, the *Aeneid*, the insights..."

For Latin-teaching resources, Laura Gibbs offers a wealth of blogs via her parent blog, *Bestiaria Latina*.⁸⁸ Her blogs include: [AudioLatinProverbs.com](http://www.audiolatinproverbs.com/), [AudioLatin.com](http://www.audiolatin.com/), [LatinViaFables.com](http://www.latinviafables.com/),

⁸⁶ <http://www.carminacatulli.blogspot.com/>

⁸⁷ <http://silemi.wordpress.com/about/>

⁸⁸ <http://bestiariablog.bestlatin.net/>

LatinViaProverbs.com and LatinCrossword.com. Gibbs specializes in teaching distance learning courses (mythology and folklore at this writing), and thrives on making Latin tools and study aides for both teachers and students. Through her blogs, she encourages the teaching of Latin with proverbs, fables, and puzzles, and has begun to record her readings of Latin passages for study. To Gibbs, Latin is to be learned through a multi-media approach including images (check out the 17th-century woodcuts that accompany her Aesop's fables), audio and reading passages from ancient authors.

The most difficult thing about blogs is not their creation (which can take anywhere from five to thirty minutes), but their upkeep. Content must be fresh and ever-changing, so that the audience keeps coming back for more, eager to read and learn. As with any endeavor (such as writing a thesis or dissertation), setting a schedule is key. Spending even 30 minutes a day to manage your blog, or to write a few lines is enough to get started. If you have tied the blog to your classes, you and your students will drive each other to create content on a regular basis, especially if the content is to be graded.

Conclusion

In the June 19, 2007, edition of the *St. Louis Post-Dispatch*, Jonathan Fanton, president of the John D. and Catherine T. MacArthur Foundation, wrote in his article "New Generations, New Media Challenges," "Today's young people increasingly express themselves and build communities with the powerful tools of technology." He continues, noting that "the real gap between tomorrow's digital haves and have-nots will be a lag in competence and confidence in the fast-paced and variegated new digital universe that is building and breeding outside schoolhouse walls. Our challenge is to harness these educational forces, opening our classrooms to the learning in which children now engage largely outside of school."

As technology changes and new generations of students adopt their gadgets and software for play, we as educators and providers of pedagogical content must not turn a blind eye to these advances. To reach our students in their new vernacular and to maintain their interest in Classics, we must be responsible in training ourselves in the use of new technology for education. It would be elitist to demand that students cast off the media they have grown up with in order to learn via older methods. While those methods held true for students of another age, we must continue to adapt our approach to teaching to new approaches to learning, meeting in the middle.

The classic argument is that things were better 20, 50, 100 years ago, and that we knew how to do things right back then: "Kids today are so different." The truth is that pedagogy may not get better or worse over time, but it does change. Whether we choose to see this

difference as an improvement or a detriment to the teaching of Classics is up to us. I say go with the flow and adapt. Horace's words remain the same, but how those words are delivered, and how their content and context are interpreted will always be in flux.

Think of studying on wax-covered slates when one could do so on papyrus or parchment. Think of taking notes on papyrus or parchment when one could do so on paper. Think of making notes in a scroll when one could use a codex. Think of working from a static book, when one could use the ever-evolving Internet. Think of using the Internet, when one could use ...? There will always be a then, a now, and a next, to enable us to reach greater heights more quickly. Technology was not meant to slow us down or to be a hindrance. We are now caught up in a revolution not unlike the moment when humanity moved from manuscript codex to printed book. This is the most optimistic of human endeavors: to develop tools to take us forward into the next Age.

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